

Evolving Needs, Evolving Services: A Comparative Evaluation of the Office of Student Affairs and Services Programs of San Isidro College

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ABSTRACT

The comprehensive services offered by the Office of Student Affairs and Services (SAS) play a crucial role in supporting student welfare, development, and institutional needs to create a conducive learning environment. By evaluating the implementation and effectiveness of these services across different academic years, the research identifies strengths and areas for improvement to ensure they meet students' diverse needs and to provide insights and recommendations for enhancing student support systems within academic institutions. The study used a cross-sectional research design to compare the office of SAS programs across two academic years at San Isidro College. The study employed stratified random sampling to ensure representative participation from different courses. The sample includes 484 respondents from A.Y. 2022-2023 and 735 respondents from A.Y. 2023-2024. The study highlights significant improvements in student welfare, development, and institutional services at SIC between the academic years. Enhancements in various student services have led to higher levels of satisfaction and support, reflecting the effectiveness of initiatives implemented by the SAS office. Increased student engagement, better access to resources, and a more supportive campus environment are notable outcomes of these improvements. The SAS office's continuous efforts to assess and upgrade services have been successful in meeting evolving student needs. Overall, these advancements contribute to a holistic educational experience, promoting student retention, satisfaction, and success.

Keywords: *institutional student program and services, office of student affairs and services, student development services, student evaluation, student welfare services*

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

The Office of Student Affairs and Services (SAS) provides a wide range of essential services designed to support and enhance the overall student experience within an academic institution (Tan, 2021). These services encompass various aspects of student life, including welfare (Galvez, 2018), development (Laroya, 2021), and institutional programs (Bucad & Perez, 2021), all aimed at fostering a conducive learning environment (Arangote, 2018). The significance of these services lies in their ability to address the diverse needs of students, thereby promoting their academic success, personal growth, and well-being, which are critical to the effective functioning of any educational institution (Tan & Prado, 2020).

Student welfare services are one of the cornerstones of an academic institution's support system, designed to guide students through their academic journey with essential resources and assistance (Galvez, 2018; Martinez & Salonga, 2019). These services encompass a broad spectrum of support, addressing students' informational, emotional, and career-related needs to ensure their overall well-being (Sarsale, 2020). By providing a robust support network, student welfare services play a critical role in fostering students' holistic development, equipping them with the tools and resilience needed to face future challenges (Loyola, 2022).

Moreover, the student development services are dedicated to nurturing the personal growth and leadership potential of students, creating a vibrant and engaging campus life (Laroya, 2021). These services offer students numerous opportunities to participate in extracurricular activities, assume leadership roles, and develop a sense of responsibility and community (Amit, 2019). By fostering an environment that encourages active participation and personal development, student development services significantly enhance the educational experience (Magbanuaa et al., 2021; Calamayo et al., 2022). They help students become well-rounded individuals capable of contributing meaningfully to society. The transformative impact of these services extends beyond the classroom, shaping students into leaders and innovators who are prepared to make a positive difference in the world (Madero, 2020).

Furthermore, the institutional student programs and services provide the foundational infrastructure and resources essential for supporting students' academic and personal growth (Bucad & Perez, 2021). These comprehensive services ensure that students have access to a safe, nurturing environment and the resources they need to thrive. From ensuring campus safety to offering financial assistance and health services, these programs cover every aspect of student life (Java, 2020; Maslang et al., 2022). By delivering a wide array of support mechanisms, institutional student programs and services play a pivotal role in the institution's ability to deliver high-quality education (Maslang et al., 2021). They create an environment where students can focus on their studies, engage in meaningful activities, and develop into successful, well-rounded individuals (Estacio et al., 2022).

Evaluating the extent to which student affairs and services are implemented is vital for an academic institution's continuous development and improvement (Tan, 2021). Through systematic assessment, institutions can identify strengths and areas for improvement, ensuring that the services provided effectively meet students' needs. Regular evaluation helps adapt to changing

student demographics and needs, in turn enhancing the overall quality of education and student satisfaction.

This study aims to address the empirical gap by providing a comprehensive analysis of the implementation and effectiveness of student affairs and services and comparing the implementation from Academic Year 2022-2023 and Academic Year 2023-2024. The objective is to evaluate how well these services are integrated into the academic environment and their development. The study seeks to compare the implementation of student services and programs and formulate recommendations that can help institutions enhance their support systems and better serve their student populations.

Conceptual Framework

The research is grounded in the concept developed by UNESCO (2002) regarding the significance of student affairs and services in colleges. Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) prioritize student affairs and services to foster cognitive, social, and cultural growth through various programs. These services are crucial for creating a positive and encouraging learning community on campus, offering frameworks for academic and personal development. The Office of SAS enhances the overall student experience, supporting students' academic, personal, and social success beyond the classroom. They ensure students have access to resources and opportunities, promoting retention and success while creating a positive, secure environment for growth and achievement (Galvez, 2018; Sison, 2019; Sultana et al., 2021).

Student welfare and development services help students achieve their goals by overcoming barriers, offering extracurricular activities, and fostering discipline and character growth. These services are vital to SAS's mission of student success, contributing to students' well-being and helping them navigate college life. Institutional programs and services provide essential resources and support, creating a nurturing environment for intellectual, emotional, and social growth. By offering a variety of programs, institutions enhance students' school experience and encourage them to reach their full potential (Grant, 2021; Tan & Prado, 2020; Masserini et al., 2019).

Evolving Needs, Evolving Services: A Comparative Evaluation of the Office of Student Affairs and Services Programs of San Isidro College

Figure 1.

Conceptual Model of the Study

The conceptual framework for this study, as presented in Figure 1 and adopted from Mercado et al. (2015), uses a logic model from CMO No. 21, s. 2006, and incorporates provisions from CMO No. 9 Series of 2013 to identify independent variables: student welfare services, student development services, and institutional student programs and services. This structured approach evaluates the implementation of SAS programs, focusing on the interplay between these variables and the extent of their implementation during A.Y. 2022-2023 and A.Y. 2023-2024. The study assesses how these services meet student needs, influenced by their well-being, personal growth, and the quality of institutional services, aiming to provide insights and identify areas for improvement to support student success and development (Sison, 2019; Tan, 2021).

Statement of the Problem

The study evaluates the extent of the implementation of the services of the different offices of the Student Affairs and Services (SAS) in San Isidro College (SIC) between Academic Year 2022-2023 and Academic Year 2023-2024. Specifically, it answers the following:

1. Is there a significant difference in the implementation of the services and programs of Academic Year 2022-2023 and Academic Year 2023-2024 considering:
 - a. student welfare;
 - b. student development; and

- c. institutional programs and services?
2. Is there a significant difference between the implementation of the different student welfare services of Academic Year 2022-2023 and Academic Year 2023-2024?
3. Is there a significant difference between the implementation of the different student development services of Academic Year 2022-2023 and Academic Year 2023-2024?
4. Is there a significant difference between the implementation of the different institutional student programs and services of Academic Year 2022-2023 and Academic Year 2023-2024?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study utilizes a cross-sectional research design (Spector, 2019). This design involves collecting data at a single point in time from different cohorts, allowing for a comparative analysis of the Student Affairs and Services (SAS) programs across two academic years, A.Y. 2022-2023 and A.Y. 2023-2024. The design allowed the study to effectively capture the differences and similarities in the implementation and effectiveness of these programs, providing insights into how the services have evolved and how they impact the student body.

Sample, Sampling Technique, and Research Instrument

The study employed stratified random sampling (Koyuncu & Kadilar, 2009) to ensure representative participation from the diverse student population at San Isidro College (SIC). The strata are defined by the different courses offered, ensuring that each course has a proportional representation in the sample. This technique allows for a more accurate reflection of the entire student body's perspectives on the office of SAS programs.

The research instrument used in this study is an adapted version of the questionnaire developed by Tan (2021), with modifications to better suit the context of SIC. The questionnaire was pilot-tested to ensure its reliability and validity, resulting in a Cronbach alpha of 0.726, indicating acceptable internal consistency. The instrument was designed to gather comprehensive data on students' perceptions and experiences with the services and programs offered by the office of SAS.

The study's sample, as presented in Table 1, consists of 484 respondents for the Academic Year 2022-2023 and 735 respondents for the Academic Year 2023-2024. These respondents were officially enrolled in the various courses offered by SIC. The larger sample size in the latter academic year allows for a more robust analysis and comparison of the changes and improvements in student services and programs over time.

Table 1.
Demographic distribution of the students in the study.

Department and Courses	A.Y. 2022-2023 (N=484)		A.Y. 2023-2024 (N=735)	
	f	%	f	%
School of Arts and Sciences (SAS)				
Bachelor of Arts	32	6.6	44	6.0
School of Accountancy (SOA)				
Bachelor of Science in Accountancy	17	3.5	40	5.4
School of Business Administration (SBA)				
Bachelor of Science in Business Administration	84	17.4	59	8.0
Bachelor of Science in Office Administration	21	4.3	14	1.9
School of Education (SED)				
Bachelor of Elementary Education	85	17.6	53	7.2
Bachelor of Secondary Education	92	19.0	104	14.1
School of Engineering (SOE)				
Bachelor of Science in Civil Engineering	69	14.3	89	12.1
School of Information Technology (SIT)				
Bachelor of Science in Information Technology	16	3.3	37	5.0
School of Nursing and Midwifery (SONM)				
Bachelor of Science in Nursing	63	13.0	292	39.7
Bachelor of Science in Midwifery	5	1.0	3	0.4

Data Gathering Procedure

The data-gathering procedure for the study was conducted over one month during the last month of the second semester of each academic year. An online survey method (Toepoel, 2017) was used to collect data, ensuring broad participation and convenience for respondents. The study adhered to protocols for data gathering, including obtaining informed consent from participants and ensuring data privacy. The first phase of data collection focused on the initial evaluation of the student services, while the second phase, conducted after some initiatives were implemented, aimed to assess any changes in the implementation and effectiveness of the student services and programs.

Phase One (A.Y. 2022-2023)

During the first phase, data was gathered to evaluate the baseline status of the student services and programs offered by the Office of Student Affairs and Services. This initial evaluation provided a snapshot of the student's experiences and satisfaction with the services before any new initiatives were introduced. The feedback collected during this phase was crucial in identifying areas that required improvement and in designing interventions to enhance the quality of student services.

Phase Two (A.Y. 2023-2024)

The second phase of data collection was conducted after implementing the identified initiatives and improvements. This phase aimed to evaluate the impact of these changes on the implementation and effectiveness of the student services and programs. By comparing the data from both phases, the study was able to assess whether the initiatives led to significant improvements and how the students perceived the changes.

Data Analysis

The study employs descriptive statistics and the independent t-test to analyze the data collected. Descriptive statistics provide an overview of the general trends and patterns in the students' responses, while the independent t-test compares the implementation of the services and programs between A.Y. 2022-2023 and A.Y. 2023-2024. This comparative analysis allows the study to identify significant differences and improvements in the student services and programs, providing insights into the effectiveness of the implemented initiatives and informing future enhancements.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Implementation of the Services and Programs

Table 2 compares the implementation of the student welfare services, student development services, and the institutional student program and services of the office of Student Affairs and Services (SAS) during A.Y. 2022-2023 and A.Y. 2023-2024 at San Isidro College (SIC).

Table 2.

Comparison of the implementation of student services and programs.

Academic Year	Student Welfare Services			Student Development Services			Institutional Student Programs and Services		
	\bar{x}	t	p	\bar{x}	t	p	\bar{x}	t	p
A.Y. 2022-2023	3.40			3.49			3.47		
A.Y. 2023-2024	3.74	-4.450	0.000*	3.75	-3.310	0.001*	3.76	-3.791	0.000*

NOTE: * $p < 0.01$

Table 3 presents the mean score, standard deviation, and qualitative interpretation of the implementation of the student services and programs at SIC during A.Y. 2022-2023 and A.Y. 2023-2024.

Table 3.

Student mean score on the implementation of student services and programs.

Services	A.Y. 2022-2023			A.Y. 2023-2024		
	\bar{x}	σ_x	Q.I.	\bar{x}	σ_x	Q.I.
Institutional Student Programs and Services	3.47	1.411	V	3.76	1.099	V
Student Development Services	3.49	1.446	V	3.75	1.160	V
Student Welfare Services	3.40	1.401	M	3.74	1.144	V

LEGEND: Q.I. – Qualitative Interpretation

G – Implemented to a Great Extent

V – Implemented to a Very Good Extent

M – Implemented to a Moderate Extent

F – Implemented to a Fair Extent

L – Implemented to a Little Extent

Students Welfare Services

As presented in Table 2 and Table 3, the result indicated that there was a significant difference between the implementation of the student welfare services of A.Y. 2022-2023 ($M=3.40$, $SD=1.411$) and A.Y. 2023-2024 ($M=3.76$, $SD=1.099$), $t(887.89)=-4.450$, $p=0.000$. The result suggests that the initiatives and enhancements introduced in student welfare services have been

Evolving Needs, Evolving Services: A Comparative Evaluation of the Office of Student Affairs and Services Programs of San Isidro College

effective, leading to higher levels of satisfaction and perceived quality among students. This improvement highlights the importance of continuously assessing and upgrading student welfare programs to meet evolving student needs (Tan & Prado, 2020). Consequently, this progress positively impacts the overall function of SIC by fostering a supportive and nurturing environment that contributes to students' academic success and well-being (Bucad & Perez, 2021; Guaimalon et al., 2022).

Student Development Services

As presented in Table 2 and Table 3, the result indicated that there was a significant difference between the implementation of the student development services of A.Y. 2022-2023 (M=3.49, SD=1.446) and A.Y. 2023-2024 (M=3.75, SD=1.160), $t(875.93)=-3.310$, $p=0.001$. The result underscores the effectiveness of the enhancements made in the student development area. This improvement reflects the increased opportunities for students to engage in extracurricular activities, develop leadership skills, and participate in school initiatives (Galvez, 2018; Amit, 2019). The positive change in student development services implies that the office of SAS is successfully creating a vibrant campus life that promotes personal growth and development (Bucad & Perez, 2021).

Institutional Student Programs and Services

As presented in Table 2 and Table 3, the result indicated that there was a significant difference between the implementation of the institutional student program and services during A.Y. 2022-2023 (M=3.40, SD=1.401) and A.Y. 2023-2024 (M=3.74, SD=1.144), $t(855.82)=-3.791$, $p=0.000$. This improvement indicates that the college's efforts to bolster institutional support mechanisms, such as student aid, services, and academic resources, have been successful. The increased effectiveness of these programs suggests that students now have better access to essential resources that aid their academic and personal development (Galvez, 2018; Java, 2020). This progress is critical for the office of SAS, as it ensures that the institution can provide a comprehensive support system that enhances the overall student experience, thereby contributing to SIC's academic and operational excellence (Bernardo & Baranovich, 2016; Bucad & Perez, 2021; Maslang et al., 2022).

Student Services and Programs

The results demonstrate significant improvements across all three areas of student services at SIC, with the most substantial gains observed in institutional student programs and services (mean increase from 3.47 to 3.76), followed by student development services (mean increase from 3.49 to 3.75), and student welfare services (mean increase from 3.40 to 3.74). These findings indicate that the initiatives implemented by the office of SAS have been effective in enhancing the quality and effectiveness of the services provided to students.

The improvements suggest that students are benefiting from more robust support systems, increased opportunities for personal growth, and better access to essential resources (Arangote, 2018; Maslang et al., 2021; Calamayo et al., 2022). Enhanced student services contribute to a more supportive and engaging campus environment, which is crucial for student retention, satisfaction, and success (Martinez & Salonga, 2019; Loyola, 2022). By continuously improving and adapting

its services, the SAS office plays a vital role in fostering a holistic educational experience that prepares students for future challenges (Galvez, 2018; Sarsale, 2020; Tan, 2021).

Implementation of the Different Student Welfare Services

Table 4 compares the implementation of the information and orientation services, guidance and counseling services, and career placement services under the student welfare services of the office of SAS during the A.Y. 2022-2023 and A.Y. 2023-2024 at SIC.

Table 4.
Comparison of the implementation of the student welfare services.

Academic Year	Information and Orientation Services			Guidance and Counseling Services			Career and Placement Services		
	\bar{x}	t	p	\bar{x}	t	p	\bar{x}	t	p
A.Y. 2022-2023	3.36			3.43			3.40		
A.Y. 2023-2024	3.72	-4.462	0.000*	3.79	-4.463	0.000*	3.72	-4.017	0.000*

NOTE: * $p < 0.01$

Table 5 presents the mean score, standard deviation, and qualitative interpretation of the implementation of the student welfare services at SIC during A.Y. 2022-2023 and A.Y. 2023-2024.

Table 5.
Student mean score on the implementation of student welfare services.

Student Welfare Services	A.Y. 2022-2023			A.Y. 2023-2024		
	\bar{x}	σ_x	Q.I.	\bar{x}	σ_x	Q.I.
Guidance and Counseling Services	3.43	1.464	V	3.79	1.153	V
Information and Orientation Services	3.36	1.449	M	3.72	1.199	V
Career and Placement Services	3.40	1.419	M	3.72	1.194	V

LEGEND: Q.I. – Qualitative Interpretation
 G – Implemented to a Great Extent
 V – Implemented to a Very Good Extent
 M – Implemented to a Moderate Extent
 F – Implemented to a Fair Extent
 L – Implemented to a Little Extent

Information and Orientation Services

As presented in Table 4 and Table 5, the result indicated that there was a significant difference between the implementation of the information and orientation services during the A.Y. 2022-2023 ($M=3.36$, $SD=1.449$) and A.Y. 2023-2024 ($M=3.72$, $SD=1.199$), $t(896.88)=-4.462$, $p=0.000$. This significant difference suggests that the enhancements made to the information and orientation services have effectively addressed student needs, resulting in higher satisfaction levels. Improved information and orientation services ensure that students are better informed about institutional policies, programs, and resources, which is crucial for their academic and social integration (Arangote, 2018; Calamayo et al., 2022).

Guidance and Counseling Services

As presented in Table 4 and Table 5, the result indicated that there was a significant difference between the implementation of the guidance and counseling services during the A.Y. 2022-2023

Evolving Needs, Evolving Services: A Comparative Evaluation of the Office of Student Affairs and Services Programs of San Isidro College

($M=3.43$, $SD=1.464$) and A.Y. 2023-2024 ($M=3.79$, $SD=1.153$), $t(863.68)=-4.463$, $p=0.000$. This progress reflects positively on the SAS office, indicating its commitment to providing essential support that helps students navigate their academic journey more effectively (Bucad & Perez, 2021).

This result implies that the updated guidance and counseling services have successfully met students' emotional and psychological needs, leading to higher satisfaction levels. Effective guidance and counseling are vital for student well-being, helping them manage academic stress, personal issues, and career planning (Amit, 2019; Maslang et al., 2021). The positive change in this service area highlights the SAS office's role in creating a supportive environment that promotes mental health and personal growth (Arcega et al., 2017; Java, 2020; Calamayo et al., 2022).

Career and Placement Services

As presented in Table 4 and Table 5, the result indicated that there was a significant difference between the implementation of the career and placement services during the A.Y. 2022-2023 ($M=3.40$, $SD=1.419$) and A.Y. 2023-2023 ($M=3.72$, $SD=1.194$), $t(908.27)=-4.017$, $p=0.000$. This significant difference indicates that the initiatives undertaken to enhance career and placement services have been successful in better preparing students for their future careers. Improved career and placement services mean that students receive more effective guidance and support in finding internships, job placements, and career development opportunities (Arangote, 2018; Calamayo et al., 2022). This progress reflects the SAS offices' commitment to equipping students with the skills and resources needed for professional success (Estacio et al., 2022).

Student Welfare Services

The results demonstrate significant improvements across the three key areas of student welfare services at San Isidro College, with the most substantial gains observed in guidance and counseling services (mean increase from 3.43 to 3.79), followed by information and orientation services (mean increase from 3.36 to 3.72), and career and placement services (mean increase from 3.40 to 3.72). These findings indicate that the enhancements made by the SAS office have been effective in addressing student needs and improving service quality. Enhanced guidance and counseling services have successfully supported students' emotional and psychological well-being, information and orientation services have better-informed students, and career and placement services have more effectively prepared students for their future careers (Maslang et al., 2021; Calamayo et al., 2022; Estacio et al., 2022).

Improved student welfare services contribute to a supportive and nurturing campus environment, which is crucial for student satisfaction, retention, and success (Martinez & Salonga, 2019). By continuously improving these services, the SAS offices play a vital role in fostering a holistic educational experience that supports students' academic, personal, and professional growth (Sarsale, 2020; Loyola, 2022). This progress not only elevates the institution's reputation but also ensures that SIC remains committed to the comprehensive development of its students, ultimately contributing to its mission of producing well-rounded and successful graduates (Galvez, 2018).

Implementation of the Different Student Development Services

Table 6 compares the implementation of the student activity/ student organization and student discipline under the student development services of the office of SAS during the A.Y. 2022-2023 and A.Y. 2023-2024 at SIC.

Table 6.

Comparison of the implementation of student development services.

Academic Year	Student Activity / Student Organization			Student Discipline		
	\bar{x}	t	p	\bar{x}	t	p
A.Y. 2022-2023	3.48	-3.058	0.002*	3.50	-3.490	0.001*
A.Y. 2023-2024	3.72			3.77		

NOTE: * $p < 0.01$

Table 7 presents the mean score, standard deviation, and qualitative interpretation of the implementation of the student development services at SIC during A.Y. 2022-2023 and A.Y. 2023-2024.

Table 7.

Student mean score on the implementation of student development services.

Student Development Services	A.Y. 2022-2023			A.Y. 2023-2024		
	\bar{x}	σ_x	Q.I.	\bar{x}	σ_x	Q.I.
Student Discipline	3.50	1.462	V	3.77	1.153	V
Student Activity / Student Organization	3.48	1.452	V	3.72	1.211	V

LEGEND: Q.I. – Qualitative Interpretation

G – Implemented to a Great Extent

V – Implemented to a Very Good Extent

M – Implemented to a Moderate Extent

F – Implemented to a Fair Extent

L – Implemented to a Little Extent

Student Activity / Student Organization

As presented in Table 6 and Table 7, the result indicated that there was a significant difference between the implementation of the student activity/ student organization during the A.Y. 2022-2023 (M=3.48, SD=1.452) and A.Y. 2023-2024 (M=3.72, SD=1.211), $t(901.94) = -3.058$, $p = 0.002$. This significant difference indicates that the enhancements made to student activities and organizations have positively impacted student engagement and participation (Bernardo & Baranovich, 2016). Improved student activities and organizations provide students with more opportunities to develop leadership skills, build social connections, and engage in extracurricular pursuits (Arcega et al., 2017; Beltran, 2019; Madero, 2020). This progress suggests that the SAS office has been effective in creating a more vibrant and inclusive campus environment, which is essential for fostering a well-rounded educational experience (Arangote, 2018).

Student Discipline

As presented in Table 6 and Table 7, the result indicated that there was a significant difference between the implementation of the student discipline during the A.Y. 2022-2023 (M=3.50, SD=1.462) and A.Y. 2023-2024 (M=3.77, SD=1.153), $t(864.45) = -3.490$, $p = 0.001$. This significant difference suggests that the measures taken to enhance student discipline have effectively addressed behavioral issues and promoted a more respectful and orderly campus environment (Bucad & Perez, 2021). Improved student discipline is crucial for maintaining a safe and conducive

learning atmosphere, which directly impacts academic success and general student well-being (Amit, 2019; Maslang et al., 2022). The positive change in this area highlights the SAS offices' commitment to upholding high standards of conduct and fostering a positive campus culture (Bernardo & Baranovich, 2016).

Student Development Services

The results demonstrate significant improvements in both student activities/student organizations and student discipline under the student development services at SIC. The most substantial gains were observed in student discipline (mean increase from 3.50 to 3.77), followed by student activities and organizations (mean increase from 3.48 to 3.72). These findings indicate that the enhancements made by the SAS office have been effective in promoting student engagement, leadership development, and a respectful campus environment (Madero, 2020; Bucad & Perez, 2021; Maslang et al., 2022). Improved student development services contribute to a holistic educational experience, fostering personal growth and social responsibility among students (Laroya, 2021; Magbanuaa et al., 2021; Calamayo et al., 2022). By continuously improving these services, the SAS office plays a vital role in creating a vibrant and orderly campus community, which is essential for the overall function and reputation of SIC (Madero, 2020).

Implementation of the Different Institutional Student Programs and Services

Table 8 compares the implementation of the admission services, scholarship and financial assistance, food services, health services, safety and security services, faith services, sports development services, social and community involvement programs, library services, information and communication technology services, registry and students' information services, and business office services under the institutional student programs and services of the office of SAS during the A.Y. 2022-2023 and A.Y. 2023-2024 at SIC.

Table 8.
Comparison of the implementation of the institutional student programs and services.

Academic Year	Admission Services		Scholarship and Financial Assistance		Food Services		Health Services		
	\bar{x}	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	\bar{x}	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	\bar{x}	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
A.Y. 2022-2023	3.43	-3.480	0.001*	3.36	-4.975	0.000*	3.30	-5.235	0.000*
A.Y. 2023-2024	3.71			3.75			3.71		0.002*
									3.77
Academic Year	Safety and Security Services		Faith Services		Sport Development Services		Social and Community Involvement Programs		
	\bar{x}	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	\bar{x}	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	\bar{x}	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
A.Y. 2022-2023	3.54	-3.109	0.002*	3.57	-2.791	0.005*	3.46	-3.365	0.001*
A.Y. 2023-2024	3.79			3.80			3.73		0.001*
Academic Year	Library Services		Information and Communication Technology Services		Registry and Students' Information Services		Business Office Services		
	\bar{x}	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	\bar{x}	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	\bar{x}	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
A.Y. 2022-2023	3.53	-4.002	0.000*	3.52	-2.880	0.004*	3.41	-4.209	0.000*
A.Y. 2023-2024	3.85			3.75			3.75		0.001*

NOTE: **p*<0.01

Evolving Needs, Evolving Services: A Comparative Evaluation of the Office of Student Affairs and Services Programs of San Isidro College

Table 9 presents the mean score, standard deviation, and qualitative interpretation of the implementation of the institutional student programs and services of the office of SAS during at SIC during the A.Y. 2022-2023 and A.Y. 2023-2024.

Table 9.
Student mean score on the institutional student programs and services.

Services	A.Y. 2022-2023			A.Y. 2023-2024		
	\bar{x}	σ_x	Q.I.	\bar{x}	σ_x	Q.I.
Library Services	3.53	1.445	V	3.85	1.158	V
Faith Services	3.57	1.505	V	3.80	1.170	V
Safety and Security Services	3.54	1.484	V	3.79	1.163	V
Business Office Services	3.52	1.447	V	3.78	1.157	V
Health Services	3.52	1.477	V	3.77	1.174	V
Information and Communication Technology Services	3.52	1.458	V	3.75	1.163	V
Registry and Students' Information Services	3.41	1.528	V	3.75	1.157	V
Scholarship and Financial Assistance	3.36	1.429	M	3.75	1.149	V
Social and Community Involvement Programs	3.48	1.452	V	3.74	1.139	V
Sport Development Services	3.46	1.465	V	3.73	1.157	V
Admission Services	3.43	1.428	V	3.71	1.208	V
Food Services	3.30	1.431	M	3.71	1.147	V

LEGEND: Q.I. – Qualitative Interpretation

G – Implemented to a Great Extent

V – Implemented to a Very Good Extent

M – Implemented to a Moderate Extent

F – Implemented to a Fair Extent

L – Implemented to a Little Extent

Admission Services

As presented in Table 8 and Table 9, the result indicated that there was a significant difference between the implementation admission services during the A.Y. 2022-2023 (M=3.43, SD=1.428) and A.Y. 2023-2024 (M=3.71, SD=1.208), $t(912.02)=-3.480$, $p=0.001$. This significant difference suggests that enhancements in admission services have made the process more efficient, user-friendly, and supportive for prospective students (Java, 2020; Maslang et al., 2021). Improved admission services likely contribute to a smoother transition for new students, positively impacting their initial impression and overall satisfaction with SIC (Bucad & Perez, 2021; Gaitan & Laganhon, 2022). This advancement reflects the SAS offices' commitment to improving administrative processes, which is crucial for attracting and retaining students, thus supporting the overall function and growth of the institution (Campos & Campos, 2023).

Scholarship and Financial Assistance

As presented in Table 8 and Table 9, the result indicated that there was a significant difference between the implementation of the scholarship and financial assistance during the A.Y. 2022-2023 (M=3.36, SD=1.429) and A.Y. 2023-2024 (M=3.75, SD=1.149), $t(877.57)=-4.975$, $p=0.000$. This improvement highlights the effectiveness of initiatives aimed at providing financial support to students, making education more accessible, and reducing financial barriers (Java, 2020; Maslang et al., 2021). Enhanced scholarship and financial assistance services are crucial for ensuring that students from diverse economic backgrounds can pursue their education without undue financial stress (Arangote, 2018; Campos & Campos, 2023). This progress underscores the SAS offices' role in promoting educational equity and supporting SIC's overall mission to provide inclusive and accessible education (Tan, 2021).

Food Services

As presented in Table 8 and Table 9, the result indicated that there was a significant difference between the implementation of the food services during the A.Y. 2022-2023 (M=3.30, SD=1.431) and A.Y. 2023-2024 (M=3.71, SD=1.147), $t(875.27)=-5.235$, $p=0.000$. This notable improvement indicates that enhancements to the food services have led to better quality, variety, and accessibility of food options for students (Tejero-Dakay et al., 2024). Improved food services contribute to students' overall well-being and satisfaction, creating a more supportive and comfortable campus environment (Arcega et al., 2017; Sarsale, 2020). The SAS offices' focus on improving these services reflects a commitment to addressing students' basic needs, which is essential for their academic success and overall campus experience, thereby enhancing the institution's reputation and appeal (Amit, 2019; Java, 2020).

Health Services

As presented in Table 8 and Table 9, the result indicated that there was a significant difference between the implementation of the health services during A.Y. 2022-2023 (M=3.52, SD=1.477) and A.Y. 2023-2024 (M=3.77, SD=1.174), $t(869.82)=-3.096$, $p=0.002$. This significant difference suggests that improvements in health services have made healthcare more accessible and responsive to student needs (Arcega et al., 2017). Enhanced health services are vital for maintaining student health, which directly impacts their academic performance and overall well-being (Cleofas, 2020; Calamayo et al., 2022). The positive changes in this area reflect the SAS offices' dedication to fostering a healthy campus environment, which is crucial for the overall functioning of SIC by ensuring that students can focus on their studies without health-related disruptions (Campos & Campos, 2023).

Safety and Security Services

As presented in Table 8 and Table 9, the result indicated that there was a significant difference between the implementation of the safety and security services during the A.Y. 2022-2023 (M=3.54, SD=1.484) and A.Y. 2023-2024 (M=3.79, SD=1.163), $t(860.58)=-3.109$, $p=0.002$. This significant enhancement indicates that measures to improve campus safety and security have been effective, creating a safer and more secure environment for students and staff (Java, 2020). Improved safety and security services are essential for protecting students' physical well-being and ensuring a conducive learning environment (Arangote, 2018; Calamayo et al., 2022). The progress in this area highlights the SAS offices' commitment to maintaining a safe campus, which is fundamental to the overall function and reputation of SIC.

Faith Services

As presented in Table 8 and Table 9, the result indicated that there was a significant difference between the implementation of the faith services during the A.Y. 2022-2023 (M=3.57, SD=1.505) and A.Y. 2023-2024 (M=3.80, SD=1.170), $t(854.96)=-2.791$, $p=0.005$. This significant difference indicates that the initiatives to support students' spiritual needs have been effective, providing more robust and accessible faith services (Amit, 2019). Enhanced faith services contribute to students' holistic development by addressing their spiritual well-being, fostering a sense of community, and promoting moral values (Bernardo & Baranovich, 2016; Bucad & Perez, 2021; Diana et al., 2023). The SAS offices' efforts in this area reflect a commitment to supporting the diverse needs of the

student body, which is essential for creating an inclusive and supportive campus environment and enhancing the overall function of SIC (Estacio et al., 2022).

Sport Development Services

As presented in Table 8 and Table 9, the result indicated that there was a significant difference between the implementation of the sports and development services during A.Y. 2022-2023 (M=3.46, SD=1.465) and A.Y. 2023-2024 (M=3.73, SD=1.157), $t(865.43)=-3.365$, $p=0.001$. This significant difference suggests that enhancements in sports programs and facilities have effectively promoted physical fitness and active lifestyles among students (Bucad & Perez, 2021). Improved sports development services provide students with more opportunities to participate in physical activities, enhancing their overall well-being and fostering teamwork and leadership skills (Arcega, 2017; Galvez, 2018; Calamayo et al., 2022). The SAS offices' focus on sports development is crucial for promoting a balanced and healthy lifestyle, which contributes to the overall function and appeal of SIC (Amit, 2019; Campos & Campos, 2023).

Social and Community Involvement Programs

As presented in Table 8 and Table 9, the result indicated that there was a significant difference between the implementation of the social and community involvement programs during the A.Y. 2022-2023 (M=3.48, SD=1.452) and A.Y. 2023-2024 (M=3.74, SD=1.139), $t(860.59)=-3.312$, $p=0.001$. This significant enhancement indicates that efforts to engage students in community service and social initiatives have been successful, fostering a sense of civic responsibility and community engagement (Bucad & Perez, 2021). Improved social and community involvement programs encourage students to contribute positively to society, enhancing their personal growth and social awareness (Cleofas, 2020; Calamayo et al., 2022). The SAS offices' initiatives in this area are vital for developing well-rounded individuals who are prepared to make meaningful contributions to their communities, thus supporting the overall mission of SIC (Bernardo & Baranovich, 2016; Amit, 2019).

Library Services

As presented in Table 8 and Table 9, the result indicated that there was a significant difference between the implementation of the library services during A.Y. 2022-2023 (M=3.53, SD=1.445) and A.Y. 2023-2024 (M=3.85, SD=1.158), $t(874.95)=-4.002$, $p=0.000$. This notable enhancement suggests that the library has become more effective in providing resources, study spaces, and support services for students (Sarsale, 2020; Calamayo et al., 2022; Estacio et al., 2022). Improved library services are critical for academic success, as they offer essential resources for research and study (Pila et al., 2016). The SAS offices' dedication to enhancing the library reflects its commitment to supporting student's academic needs, which is fundamental to the educational mission and overall function of SIC (Arcega et al., 2017; Java, 2020).

Information and Communication Technology Services

As presented in Table 8 and Table 9, the result indicated that there was a significant difference between the implementation of the information and communication technology services during the A.Y. 2022-2023 (M=3.52, SD=1.458) and A.Y. 2023-2024 (M=3.75, SD=1.163), $t(871.98)=-2.880$, $p=0.004$. This significant difference suggests that enhancements in ICT services have effectively supported students' academic and administrative needs, providing better access to

technology and online resources (Bucad & Perez, 2021). Improved ICT services are crucial for modern education, facilitating learning, communication, and administrative processes (Son & Amparado, 2018; Calamayo et al., 2022). The SAS offices' efforts in this area reflect a commitment to leveraging technology to enhance the educational experience, which is vital for SIC's overall function and competitiveness (Sarsale, 2020).

Registry and Students' Information Services

As presented in Table 8 and Table 9, the result indicated that there was a significant difference between the implementation of the registry and student information services during A.Y. 2022-2023 (M=3.41, SD=1.528) and A.Y. 2023-2024 (M=3.75, SD=1.157), $t(838.41)=-4.209$, $p=0.000$. This significant improvement indicates that the registry has become more efficient and responsive in managing student records and information (Arcega et al., 2017). Enhanced registry and student information services are essential for maintaining accurate records, facilitating academic processes, and ensuring that students can easily access their information (Bernardo & Baranovich, 2016; Arangote, 2018; Grepon et al., 2021). The SAS offices' improvements in this area are crucial for effective administrative support, contributing to the smooth operation and overall function of SIC (Campos & Campos, 2023).

Business Office Services

As presented in Table 8 and Table 9, the result indicated that there was a significant difference between the implementation of the business office services during the A.Y. 2022-2023 (M=3.52, SD=1.447) and A.Y. 2023-2024 (M=3.78, SD=1.157), $t(873.62)=-3.256$, $p=0.001$. This significant difference suggests that enhancements in business office services have made financial transactions and administrative processes more efficient and user-friendly (Cleofas, 2020). Improved business office services are essential for managing the financial and administrative aspects of students' academic lives, ensuring that transactions are processed smoothly and efficiently (Arcega et al., 2017; Grepon et al., 2021). The SAS offices' focus on improving these services reflects a commitment to operational excellence, which supports SIC's overall function and sustainability (Campos & Campos, 2023).

Institutional Student Programs and Services

The Institutional Student Programs and Services at San Isidro College reveal significant improvements across various domains, highlighting the SAS offices' commitment to enhancing the student experience. The highest-rated service improvements were observed in library services (M=3.53 to M=3.85), reflecting the college's dedication to providing essential academic resources and support (Pila et al., 2016). Faith services (M=3.57 to M=3.80) and safety and security services (M=3.54 to M=3.79) also showed substantial gains, indicating a strong focus on supporting students' spiritual needs and ensuring a safe campus environment (Bernardo & Baranovich, 2016; Calamayo et al., 2022; Diana et al., 2023).

Further improvements were noted in business office services (M=3.52 to M=3.78), health services (M=3.52 to M=3.77), and information and communication technology services (M=3.52 to M=3.75), which are crucial for efficient administrative support and student well-being (Arcega et al., 2017; Son & Amparado, 2018; Cleofas, 2020). The positive changes in these areas suggest that the Office of Student Affairs and Services has successfully addressed key operational aspects,

Evolving Needs, Evolving Services: A Comparative Evaluation of the Office of Student Affairs and Services Programs of San Isidro College

contributing to a more supportive and responsive campus environment (Tan, 2021; Campos & Campos, 2023).

Significant advancements were also seen in registry and student information services (M=3.41 to M=3.75), scholarship and financial assistance (M=3.36 to M=3.75), and social and community involvement programs (M=3.48 to M=3.74). These improvements reflect the college's efforts to ensure accurate record-keeping, provide financial support, and promote civic engagement among students (Arangote, 2018; Cleofas, 2020; Grepon et al., 2021). Enhanced sports development services (M=3.46 to M=3.73) further emphasize the importance of physical well-being and teamwork in the student development agenda (Galvez, 2018).

The lowest-rated yet significantly improved services were admission services (M=3.43 to M=3.71) and food services (M=3.30 to M=3.71). These enhancements suggest that the college has made strides in making the admissions process more efficient and ensuring better-quality food services for students (Sarsale, 2020; Gaitan & Laganhon, 2022; Tejero-Dakay et al., 2024). Overall, these improvements across various student services underscore the SAS offices' vital role in enhancing institutional effectiveness and student satisfaction at SIC, contributing to its overall function and reputation (Tan & Prado, 2020; Estacio et al., 2022; Maslang et al., 2022).

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The results indicate significant improvements in the implementation of student welfare services between the academic years 2022-2023 and 2023-2024. Enhancements in Information and Orientation Services, Guidance and Counseling Services, and Career and Placement Services led to higher levels of student satisfaction. These improvements suggest that students feel better informed, supported emotionally and psychologically, and are better prepared for their future careers. The positive changes underscore the importance of continuously assessing and upgrading student welfare programs to meet evolving needs.

The study reveals notable progress in student development services, particularly in student activities/organizations and student discipline. Enhanced student activities and organizations have increased student engagement and leadership development, while improved discipline measures have promoted a respectful and orderly campus environment. These developments contribute to a vibrant campus life that fosters personal growth, social responsibility, and a positive campus culture. The SAS office's efforts in these areas have been effective in creating an inclusive and engaging environment for students.

Significant improvements were also observed in institutional student programs and services. Enhanced admission services, scholarship and financial assistance, food services, health services, safety and security services, and other support mechanisms have effectively met student needs. These advancements have made various services more accessible, efficient, and supportive, contributing to students' academic and personal development. The improvements in these areas reflect the SAS office's commitment to providing comprehensive support that enhances the overall student experience and institutional excellence.

Overall, the services and programs offered by the SAS office at SIC have shown significant improvements across all evaluated areas. These enhancements have led to higher student satisfaction and better support systems, promoting a supportive and engaging campus

environment. The continuous improvements in student welfare, development, and institutional services indicate the SAS office's dedication to fostering a holistic educational experience. This progress is crucial for student retention, satisfaction, and success, ultimately contributing to the institution's mission of producing well-rounded and successful graduates. Although all services are performing satisfactorily, an opportunity exists to further enhance student evaluation. By improving existing services and implementing new technology or methods, the institution can strive for excellence in the different services it offers.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To further enhance Student Welfare Services at San Isidro College, it is recommended to increase the availability and accessibility of Information and Orientation Services. This can be achieved by implementing more comprehensive online resources and holding regular workshops and orientation sessions for both new and returning students. Additionally, enhancing the Guidance and Counseling Services by hiring more counselors and mental health practitioners and integrating mental health awareness programs into the curriculum can provide better emotional and psychological support. Career and Placement Services could focus on establishing stronger partnerships with local businesses and industries to create more internship and employment opportunities for students. Regular feedback mechanisms, such as surveys and focus groups, should be instituted to continually assess and improve these services based on student needs and experiences.

To improve Student Development Services, SIC could expand the scope and variety of student activities and organizations. The activity could include more diverse clubs and societies that cater to a wide range of interests, ensuring inclusivity and engagement across the student body. Training and development programs for student leaders could be enhanced to build leadership skills and foster a sense of responsibility and community among students. For Student Discipline, it is crucial to implement a clear, fair, and consistent disciplinary policy that emphasizes restorative justice practices. Educational campaigns on campus behavior expectations and conflict resolution can help maintain a respectful and orderly campus environment. These initiatives would contribute to a holistic development experience, promoting personal growth and social responsibility.

The Institutional Student Programs and Services could be improved by streamlining admission processes through the use of advanced digital platforms that ensure efficiency and accessibility. Enhancing the Scholarship and Financial Assistance programs by increasing funding opportunities for scholarships and financial aid can be achieved by actively seeking partnerships with alumni and local businesses and organizations. Moreover, simplifying application procedures which involves creating an online portal where students can easily apply for multiple scholarships with a single application, track their application status, and receive timely updates.

Upgrading Food Services to offer a wider variety of healthy and affordable meal options and extending dining hours can accommodate students' varying schedules. Regularly gathering feedback through surveys and suggestion boxes can ensure that the food services continually meet the evolving needs and preferences of the student body. Improving Health Services by hiring more staff can reduce wait times and provide more comprehensive care. Moreover, providing health education programs and wellness workshops can empower students to make informed decisions about their health. Ensuring robust Safety and Security Services by installing additional

Evolving Needs, Evolving Services: A Comparative Evaluation of the Office of Student Affairs and Services Programs of San Isidro College

surveillance cameras in common areas such as hallways, student centers, and parking lots can deter crime and enhance student safety. Implementing a mobile app that allows students to quickly report incidents and receive real-time updates on campus security can improve communication and response times. Conducting regular safety drills and providing clear, accessible emergency guides and hall maps can better prepare students for various emergency scenarios. These measures foster a safer campus environment, enhancing students' sense of security and well-being.

Promoting Faith Services by organizing retreats, recollections, and spiritual activities that cater to a variety of religious beliefs can create an inclusive environment that respects and supports students' diverse spiritual needs. Additionally, providing access to spiritual counseling and support through chaplaincy services can help students navigate personal and spiritual challenges. Regularly engaging with student religious organizations to gather feedback and tailor programs to their needs ensures that Faith Services remains relevant and supportive. To enhance the Sports Development Services, the SAS office could invest in state-of-the-art sports facilities and equipment to ensure students have access to the best resources for training and physical activity. Additionally, offering a wider range of sports and fitness programs, including intramural leagues, wellness workshops, and specialized training sessions, can cater to diverse interests and promote a healthy lifestyle. Regular surveys and feedback from student-athletes and participants can help tailor programs to meet their needs and preferences, ensuring high levels of engagement and satisfaction.

To develop the Social and Community Involvement Programs by developing partnerships with local organizations and nonprofits to provide students with more diverse and impactful volunteer opportunities. Organizing events and workshops that focus on social responsibility, civic engagement, and leadership development can empower students to become active contributors to their communities. Gathering feedback from participants can help identify areas for improvement and ensure that the programs remain relevant and meaningful. To enhance the Library Services the implementation of an intuitive online catalog and search system can make it easier for students to find and access resources. To improve ICT Services, the college could develop user-friendly platforms and mobile applications for accessing academic resources, administrative services, and campus information to enhance the overall digital experience.

To improve the Registry and Student Information Services, the office can digitize records and streamline administrative processes through an integrated student information system. Regular feedback from students on the usability and functionality of these services can help identify pain points and drive continuous improvements, making administrative interactions more efficient and user-friendly. To improve the transaction for the Business Office Services, the college could introduce online payment systems that enable students to handle tuition fees and other financial transactions securely and conveniently. Implementing a transparent and efficient billing system, along with clear communication about payment policies and deadlines, can reduce confusion and enhance trust.

Building on this study's findings, further research could explore the long-term impacts of enhanced student services on academic performance and overall student satisfaction. Comparative studies with other institutions can provide valuable insights into best practices and areas for improvement. Additionally, in-depth qualitative studies involving student interviews and focus groups can offer a deeper understanding and perspectives on student needs and experiences. These

further studies would contribute to the continuous improvement and success of student affairs and services at SIC.

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Evolving Needs, Evolving Services: A Comparative Evaluation of the Office of Student Affairs and Services Programs of San Isidro College

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